

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Kajal Containing Cow Urine

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Abstract

Traditionally, kajal is designed as a cosmetic product for enhancing the beauty of eyes and also as a medicinal product to treat eye ailments such as irritation, eye inflammation, redness, dryness etc. Kajal is mostly in the form of paste and sometimes in cake form, which is modified as sticks for easy application. They are prepared using soot of oils and herbs. The kajal is evaluated by different parameters like such as physical description, pH, viscosity, spreadability, stability studies, evaluation of bases, TLC of extracts and in-vitro studies. Findings revealed that the test product afforded a decent antimicrobial efficacy and was cosmetically acceptable as indicated by pH, viscosity and particle size analysis and physical evaluation. The present study covers formulation of Herbal kohl containing cow urine arka, Triphala, Rosa rubiginosa, Almonds powder, Coconut oil and Ghee. This is the first study that involve cow urine as one of the ingredient of kajal.

Key words: *Herbal Kajal, Cow Urine Arka, Triphala Extract, Antimicrobial Activity, Ophthalmic Formulation.*

INTRODUCTION

Kajal is worn for a variety of reasons, including culture and beauty, to prevent "evil eyes." People use kajal in the eyes of children to drive away evil as a symbol of protection. In the Ayurvedic language, kajal is known as Anjanam or eye ointment. There are many types of medicinal plants used for eye diseases. The fight against eye diseases and side-effect-free chemicals remains a challenge for the healthcare system. However, Ayurvedic herbs have the power to overcome the limitations associated with traditional medicines. For this reason, great efforts have been made to identify new medicinal plants. This is because its effectiveness, side effects are relatively small, and its cost is relatively low. A popular eye product, kohl is described in almost all human cultures as being cool and clean for the eyes and used for the prevention and treatment of eye diseases.

Benefits of applying medicated kajal:

- Nourish stressful, raw, injured eyes.
- Give cooling effect to the eyes.
- Formulation is used as anti inflammatory agent
- It is use in treatment for eye redness or Itchy eye. Increase circulation in eyes and provide better nutrition to cell.

In this formulation, Triphala herbs were selected to formulate kajal from a variety of extracts. The polyherb composition is known from Ayurveda Triphala. The triphala is composition of the Amalaki (*Emblica officinalis*), Vibhitaka (*Terminalia bellerica*), Haritaki (*Terminalia chebula*). Triphala is most commonly associated with phenolic acids, flavonoids, and tannins. The antioxidant effects shows gallic acid, esoteric acid, and ascorbic acid. The effects of rose water is cooling, cell loss protection, dark circles are remove, also comfortable for eyes and eye washing. Literatures are available stating the importance of Gomutra for all purposes in our daily life which is used since ancient times for curing many ailments of human beings. Gomutra (Sanskrit: gomūtra; "cow urine") refers to the usage of cow urine for therapeutic purposes in traditional Indian medicine also used as an important component of the mixture called Panchagavya. Gomutra is used for treatment of colic, abdominal tumors, enlargement of abdomen and flatulence. For therapies such as decoction, purgation, enema, skin diseases, eye and ear disease, kidney diseases, heart diseases, stones, diabetes, liver problem, jaundice and its shows immunostimulant, bioenhancer, anticonvulsant, anticancerous, wound healing, antioxidant and

antimicrobial properties. Medicated kajal was thought to be a revolutionary solution as the cosmeceutical drug in the fight against eye infections and enzyme.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

Table 1. Composition of formulation of medicated kajal

S. No	Name of Ingredients	Quantity	Reference
	Triphala powder	1gm	Varpe P.V. et.al., 2022 Waghulde S. et.al., 2018
	Almond powder	1gm	Varpe P.V. et.al., 2022 Gupta R. et.al., 2016
	Rose Water	1ml	Varpe P.V. et.al., 2022 Waghulde S. et.al., 2018
	Cow Ghee	1gm	Varpe P.V. et.al., 2022 Waghulde S. et.al., 2018
	Mentha extract	drops	Gupta R. et.al., 2016
	Ocimum extract	drops	Gupta R. et.al., 2016
	Cow urine arka	drops	

METHOD

Varpe P.V. et.al., 2022 reported that the method of preparation was done by taking dried powder of triphala for preparing the soot. The author used muslin cloth piece, in which triphala powder and almond powder was taken and used as a wick and was lighted in a mud lamp containing

ghee. Then, lighten the lamp and kept inverted copper plate on it. Then scraped the black soot and collected in a clean, dry porcelain dish. Added rose water, ocimum extract, mentha extract and cow urine arka in black soot, add sufficient cow ghee to obtained kajal in paste form.

Evaluation of Herbal Kohl Physical Evaluation:

The formulated product afforded a shiny black color, with a characteristic odor. It was smooth and non-gritty in texture with a semisolid consistency.

PH Determination: Read as 7.2 from pH meter.

Viscosity Determinations: Using Brookfield Viscometer (Model RV and Spindle no.7).

Evaluation of Base: Vegetable ghee was evaluated for acid value, Saponification value and ester value as per I.P. 1996.

- Acid Value: Acid Value = $5.61 \times n/w$; where n = no. of ml of 0.1 M KOH required and w = weight in grams of solvent; where n = 0.5 and w = 2.0 Hence Acid value equals to $5.61 \times 0.5/2 = 1.4025$
- Saponification Value: Saponification value equals to $28.05 (b-a) / w$; Where w = weight in grams of substance, b = blank solution reading, a = sample solution reading; b = 21,

a = 4.6, w = 2.0 Therefore, Saponification value = $28.05 (21-4.6) / 2 = 230.01$

- Ester Value: Ester value = Saponification value – Acid value Hence Ester value = $230.01 - 1.4025 = 228.6075$.

Formulation of Control for Antimicrobial Studies

Composition: triphala soot (3.0 g), Chloramphenicol (1.5 g; 6 applicaps, equivalent weight = 250 mg/ applicap) and cow ghee (q.s).

Method and Rationale: carbon black was collected on a clean china dish. Chloramphenicol was incorporated in the soot and cow ghee was used to dough out the preparation. Chloramphenicol is prototypic broad spectrum antimicrobial agent. This nitrobenzene derivative is effective against a wide range of gram positive and gram negative bacteria, including most aerobic organisms and is used topically in eye infections.

Table 1. Viscosity measurements.

S.No	RPM	Dial Reading % Torque	Factor	Viscosity = Dial reading X Factor (Centipoise)
1	10	9	4000	36000
2	20	10.5	2000	21000
3	50	12	800	9600
4	100	13	400	5200
Average Viscosity: $36000+21000+9600+5200/4 = 17950$ Centipoise				

Table 3. Observations (Zone of inhibition; n=3)

S. No	Sample	Zone of inhibition diameter (cm)
1	D.W	0.0
2	S ₁	0.2
3	S ₂	0.5
4	M ₁	0.1

RESULTS

Herbal kohl was formulated and evaluated on various parameters. The pH, viscosity (Table 2), and particle size analysis followed expected significance. The base satisfied the evaluated parameter values (acid value, Saponification value and ester value) and physical evaluation was suggestive of a cosmetically appealing product. A control was formulated for antimicrobial studies and a general antibiotic assay was conducted to evaluate the comparative antimicrobial potential of the test, control, comparator and distilled water. Composition of nutrient agar I.P and cylinder plate method was employed. As evident from the diameters of zone of inhibition (Table 3) observed for each sample a comparative order of antimicrobial efficacy deduced is as follows:

S₂ > S₁ > M₁ > D.W

D.W = Distilled water

S₁ = Test (with plant extracts)

S₂ = Control (with chloramphenicol)

M₁ = Marketed preparation (identity concealed)

DISCUSSION

Maximal antimicrobial response was shown by the control formulation containing chloramphenicol (1500mg) which is a nitrobenzene derivative with broad spectrum of activity. Test formulation enriched with aqueous plant extracts showed significant antimicrobial potential which was lesser than control but greater than the marketed formulation. The marketed formulation showed antimicrobial potential lesser than the test formulation as suggestive from the zone of inhibition measurements. pH value satisfied the pH requirement for ophthalmic and particle size analysis suggested a nongritty product. Viscosity and physical evaluation complied with cos-

metic acceptability. The herbal kohl formulated with a view to serve the dual purpose of an eye cosmetic as well as keeps the eyes healthy and free from infections was evaluated on different parameters. The results of various determinations are suggestive of an acceptable and elegant product.

REFERENCES

- Hardy, A. D., Vaishnav, R., Al-Kharussi, S. S., Sutherland, H. H., & Worthing, M. A. "Composition of eye cosmetics (kohls) used in Oman." *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 60.3 (1998): 223-234.
- Cartwright-Jones, C. "Introduction to Harquus: Part 2: Kohl, kohl as traditional women's adornment in North Africa and the Middle East." *Harquus* (2005).
- Parry, C., & Eaton, J. "Kohl: A lead-hazardous eye makeup from the third world to the first world." *Environmental Health Perspectives* 94 (1991): 121-123.
- Mahmood, Z. A., Zoha, S. M. S., Usmanghani, K., Hasan, M. M., Ali, O., Jahan, S., Saeed, A., Zahid, R., & Zubair, M. "Kohl (surma): Retrospect and prospect." *Pakistan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 22.1 (2009): 107-122.
- Florida Department of Health. "Childhood Lead Poisoning Program, Screening Guidelines." (2001).
- Vaishnav, R. "An example of the toxic potential of traditional eye cosmetics." *Indian Journal of Pharmacology* 33 (2001): 46-48.
- Al-Ashban, R. M., Aslam, M., & Shah, A. H. "Kohl (surma): A toxic traditional eye cosmetic study in Saudi Arabia." *Public Health* 118 (2004): 292-298.

8. Jallad, K. N., & Hedderich, H. G. "Characterization of a hazardous eyeliner (kohl) by confocal Raman microscopy." *Journal of Hazardous Materials B124* (2005): 236-240.
9. Mohamed, K., Ahmed, G., Aly, N., & Elmoty, A. E. A. "Determination of lead in biological specimens from homicidal poisoning case by kohl (lead sulfide)." *Toxicology Letters* 172S (2007): S1-S240.
10. Habibullah, P., Mahmood, Z. A., Sualeh, M., & Zoha, S. M. S. "Studies on the chemical composition of kohl stone by X-ray diffractometer." *Pakistan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 23.1 (2010): 48-52.
11. U.S. Food & Drug Administration. "FDA/CFSAN Cosmetics – Safe use of eye products, eyelash dyes." *Fact Sheet* (August 2001).
12. University of Illinois, Eye & Ear Infirmary. "The Eye Digest." (Accessed at agingeye.net).
13. Shah, P. P., & D'Mello, P. M. "A review of medicinal uses and pharmacological effects of *Mentha piperita*." *Natural Product Radiance* 3.4 (2004): 214-221.
14. Saeed, S., & Tariq, P. "Antibacterial activities of *Mentha piperita*, *Pisum sativum* and *Momordica charantia*." *Pakistan Journal of Botany* 37.4 (2005): 997-1001.
15. Prakash, P., & Gupta, N. "Therapeutic uses of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn (Tulsi) with a note on Eugenol and its pharmacological actions: A short review." *Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology* 49.2 (2005): 125-131.
16. Tandon, V. R. "Medicinal uses and biological activities of *Vitex negundo*." *Natural Product Radiance* 4.3 (2005): 162-165.
17. Abu-Rabia, A. "Indigenous practices among Palestinians for healing eye diseases and inflammations." *Dynamis: Acta Hispanica ad Medicinam Scientiamque Historiam Illustrandam* 25 (2005): 383-401.
18. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*. Government of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. Controller of Publications, Delhi. Vol. II, Part 2 (A50-A52, A105).

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